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Hackathon as a Kickstart for Integrated ICT Engineering

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INTRODUCTION

The new Curriculum (started 2017) of ICT engineering studies is competence based and integrated (Project Based Learning). The student feedback from the first semester was collected using a questionnaire called INNOKOMP. As a result, a corrective action it was decided to make a Hackathon experiment. The first Hackathon was arranged to start the semester project. In this case, the project included courses:

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Entrepreneurship, Product Development, Embedded Programming, English Language, and Project Management. The selected learning project was based on a customer need to automate manual operations. Hackathon events' duration is usually 2-3 days. In this pilot, the Hackathon last one working day. After giving the assignment, ten project teams started to generate new ideas by the ideation method they selected to use. Students practiced different ideation methods beforehand. During the Hackathon day, student teams produced new ideas, prototypes and finally made a short sales pitch. Afterward, the Semester project was continued to finish the learning outcomes of the integrated courses. This article describes how to the student feedback was responded and what the results of the Hackathon experiment were.

1 ORGANIZING THE LEARNING TASK

1.1 Integrated courses

ICT Engineering Department renewed the Curriculum year 2017. The new Curriculum was constructed in collaboration with working life. It is competence based and uses the Project Based Learning methodology [1]. For each semester, there is a learning and/or problem-solving project, which is supported by the other courses of the semester. The selected courses are integrated into the project and build upon the knowledge intended for the semester along with the project [2], [3]. For this research, the project included courses: Entrepreneurship, Product Development, Embedded Programming, English Language, and Project Management.

1.2 Hackathon as a kickstart

From the previous ICT Engineering student feedback, some changes for the semester project timing and start had made [2]. The new idea was to use a Hackathon as a kickstart for the project. A Hackathon is an example of project-based learning methodology. Even though it is originated in technology communities, it is widely used in any kind of organizations. It is a competitive event where teams work to ideate, collaborate, design, prototype, iterate, and present a solution to a proposed challenge [4].

The word Hackathon is a term that combines the word "hack", meaning exploratory programming, designing, prototyping, and the word "marathon", meaning a long and difficult task completed in a limited period of time [5].

For this project, the creative work of the teams was organized in 5 phases that moved from the identification of a problem as an opportunity and the creation of a "prototype" as a solution. The five phases were: Inspiration, ideation, prototyping, testing, and presentation.

The end goal was to come up with a "functional" prototype to demo during the presentation, convincing the judging panel that the team's solution is the best. While the Hackathon is an event where teams are competing against each other, there is a strong focus on collaboration within the team, as well as outside for example with customers.

1.3 The Learning task

The teacher team designed a learning task for the semester project. ICT students were in their 4th semester and they had already done a project to design and develop a house with some IoT (Internet of Things)-solutions. During their first learning project, they were learned for example generic project management and basic ICT Engineering skills.

During the project, their project management skills were added with one of the agile methods, e.g. SCRUM with the other integrated courses. The designed learning project was continued with the theme to design and develop a solution for a “customer” to automate their office.

Student teams started their learning projects by establishing own companies. The customer then asked these companies a bid for an office automation. To fulfill the bid students ideated, designed, prototyped, tested, presented and had a final exhibition for the audience from local companies, other cooperatives and all university students and teachers.

2 STUDENT FEEDBACK

2.1 Self-assessment results

Commissions form the basis for solutions. The intent of the commission is to answer the requirements and goals we want the students to learn according to the curriculum. The preconditions related to teaching are determined by courses and their objectives as well as their content description that existed before the Hackathon. We must make sure that the students know and understand these preconditions, so the thought process of the students will not produce solutions that do not fit the objectives of the courses. The commission of the Hackathon event of the spring was related to intelligent systems and IoT. Figure 1 shows the study units integrated into the seasonal project.

Fig. 1. Study units integrated into the project

The technology and technical solutions were provided by Lapland University of Applied Sciences. The goal of the organizers was to enable the fruition of good ideas with adequate technical and hardware resources. Before the event, the students were introduced to the hardware platforms, sensors, actuators, and to the necessary software tools. Although trying out new approaches encouraged, the students mainly

chose resources that they were already familiar. If needed, the students utilized other resources, not provided by the university. Using other technological solutions was due to students' skills or interest. Solutions based on familiar technologies were nonetheless creative and different from each other.

It should be noted that when working with a large group of students, the teachers do not necessarily always have a direct answer to the questions raised by the students. Several issues require professional-level expertise in which case problem-solving skills and creativity are emphasized to produce unexpected technical solutions. Ideation skills used in Hackathon will be useful in later projects and in working life.

The students were requested to evaluate their development in teamwork. The questionnaire was organized three times: during the spring of the 1st year, after the Hackathon, and after the prototype of the innovated product was finished at the end of the project.

The survey was based on the set of questions developed in the national ESR project. It measures student's innovation competencies through the self-assessment. There are total 22 questions to find out the student's own opinions in the following areas: [6]

- Ability to creative problem-solving
- Comprehensive
- Goal orientation
- Cooperation skills
- Networking skills

Teamwork skills were measured by a reflection questionnaire. The questionnaire was based on questions produced during the INNOKOMP project. The following five questions related to teamwork and innovation were chosen:

- Q1: I present ideas on how the task could be carried out for the approval of others
- Q2: I present new, practical solutions for meeting the goal
- Q3: I show interest in the subject
- Q4: I act persistently for meeting the goal(s)
- Q5: I take my group members ideas into account

Questionnaires have been made in three phases during one year so that the first one at the end of the last spring project, the second one immediately after the Hackathon event and the last when the project ended. The results of the questionnaire can be seen in theTable 1 below. The sample size was very small so reliable conclusions cannot be made. In general, the answers to the questionnaire were positive and all the students showed activity during the hackathon. In all questions, the number of students who selected an excellent choice increased.

Table 1. Results of the questionnaire. The Data are presented as frequencies and percentages of the total.

	Not at all	Poor	Moderate	Good	Excellent
Q1					
<i>Baseline</i>	0	0	5 (21%)	15 (63%)	4 (17%)
<i>After the Hackathon</i>	0	1 (3%)	7 (23%)	21 (68%)	2 (6%)
<i>After the project completion</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	14 (58%)	6 (25%)
Q2					
<i>Baseline</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	18 (75%)	2 (8%)
<i>After the Hackathon</i>	0	2 (6%)	12 (39%)	13 (42%)	4 (13%)
<i>After the project completion</i>	0	1 (4%)	2 (8%)	12 (50%)	9 (38%)
Q3					
<i>Baseline</i>	0	0	10 (42%)	12 (50%)	2 (8%)
<i>After the Hackathon</i>	0	1 (3%)	8 (26%)	19 (61%)	3 (10%)
<i>After the project completion</i>	0	0	6 (25%)	13 (54%)	5 (21%)
Q4					
<i>Baseline</i>	0	0	7 (29%)	13 (54%)	4 (17%)
<i>After the Hackathon</i>	0	1 (3%)	8 (26%)	20 (65%)	2 (6%)
<i>After the project completion</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	10 (42%)	10 (42%)
Q5					
<i>Baseline</i>	0	0	2 (8%)	14 (58%)	8 (33%)
<i>After the Hackathon</i>	0	0	2 (6%)	18 (58%)	11 (35%)
<i>After the project completion</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	9 (38%)	11 (46%)

After the hackathon, uncertainty increased. Later after the end of the project, however, students felt they were better than at the baseline. The biggest development took place in question number 2 in the initiative and question number 4 about perseverance. This can be easier to see in the figures 2 and 3 below:

Fig. 2. The development of how a student presents new, practical solutions.

Fig. 3. The development of how a student shows interest in the subject.

The questionnaire included an open field for expressing the thoughts invoked by the Hackathon event in addition to the five INNCOMP questions. In this field, the students typically hoped that in the future, the commission/task would be provided earlier so that it would be better acquainted with. This set of questions will be used in the future; it is interesting to see then, how the perception of self and improvement of cooperation skills continue to evolve.

The members of the teacher team told in an interview after the Hackathon that they were positively surprised by the results. Each group came up with a different solution to the commission and the event clearly supported unifying the members of the group together. The groups seemed happy during the commission and enjoyed the innovation process. The teachers also noted that the leeway left in the goal specifications resulted in a flexible development of the product and offered an

opportunity to affect the solution of one's own team. This most likely affected positively by the motivation and overall mood of the students. In the future, it would also be useful to take advantage of cross- and multidisciplinary project teams, as has been done at the research of the Danish Technical University [7]. Teachers saw that especially business students could participate in teams and bring their own expertise through marketing and productization.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In the first time participation in Hackathon, the ideation of the students is probably not in its full potential. During the events to come, the students will probably be more confident to innovate in a more versatile manner. If the team has unified before, the confidence to present new ideas and thoughts improves. On the other hand, the critical attitude towards their own activities increases, even though it would appear that skills have been developing steadily. Finnish culture also includes self-criticism and modesty, which is also stated on the site about Finland published by the Ministry of Foreign Trade [8].

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